

The first detection of the fungal pathogen *Batrachochytrium dendrobatidis* in Norway with no evidence of population declines for great crested and smooth newts based on modeling on traditional trapping data

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Abstract

The pathogenic fungus *Batrachochytrium dendrobatidis* (Bd) causes chytridiomycosis in amphibians across the world, often leading to population declines and species extinctions. Here, we present the first detection of Bd in Norway, diagnosed using environmental DNA (eDNA) in water samples. In a genetic screening of 31 ponds in southeastern Norway for Bd, great crested newt (*Triturus cristatus*) and smooth newt (*Lissotriton vulgaris*), we detected Bd in five different localities. Resampling in one location revealed that time of sampling seemingly had a strong effect on the concentration of Bd eDNA in the water, which increased from May till June. In contrast, eDNA concentration of great crested newt decreased during the same period. Following a traditional sampling approach with traps, newts in the investigated ponds have been sampled for population estimates since 2012. We imposed a model on the catch data and contrasted the Bd-positive ponds to the Bd-negative ponds, finding no signs of population declines in the Bd-positive ponds. This could suggest either recent infection events, with animals still having low prevalence of Bd and with little time for Bd to affect the present breeding generations of newts, and/or that the two newt species are infection-tolerant. This study further highlights eDNA as a tool for early detection of invasive species.

KEYWORDS

Bd, ddPCR, eDNA, introduced species, invasive alien species, newt

1 | INTRODUCTION

Amphibian species are in decline throughout the world, where the stressors are numerous and comprise factors such as habitat destruction, climate change, and invasive species (Catenazzi, 2015). The invasive fungal pathogen *Batrachochytrium dendrobatidis* (hereafter referred to as Bd) has received considerable attention for being

one of the key drivers of amphibian population declines worldwide since the 1970s, causing the infectious skin disease chytridiomycosis (Berger et al., 1998; Scheele et al., 2019). Not all amphibians respond equally to infection, and host responses range from resistant via tolerable to susceptible, where the clinical outcome depends on the host species, the Bd strain, and other environmental determinants (Van Rooij et al., 2015).

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As the fungus is spreading fast worldwide (O'Hanlon et al., 2018), most likely through pet trade (Scheele et al., 2019), management authorities are in need for efficient monitoring tools in order to document presence and geographical distribution of Bd before trying to assess potential impact on the native species (Parker et al., 1999). Environmental DNA (eDNA) is the genetic material obtained directly from environmental samples without any obvious signs of the biological source material (Cristescu & Hebert, 2018; Thomsen et al., 2012). eDNA is becoming increasingly accepted as an effective method for detecting species in a variety of ecosystems, including soil, seawater, and freshwater (Thomsen et al., 2012). The use of eDNA is particularly useful in aquatic environments, where visual detection and quantification of both plants and wildlife can be challenging (Rees et al., 2014). This is especially true for invasive species early in their colonizing phase when they likely have low abundance and therefore are harder to catch or observe (Balasingham et al., 2018; Cristescu & Hebert, 2018; Strand et al., 2014). If invaders can be detected at an early stage, there is a higher probability of minimizing potential negative ecological effects through active management.

Norway has relatively few amphibian species. Two species of newts (great crested newt: *Triturus cristatus* and smooth newt: *Lissotriton vulgaris*), one toad (common toad; *Bufo bufo*), and three species of frogs (common frog: *Rana temporaria*, Moor frog: *R. arvalis*, and pool frog: *Pelophylax lessonae*) are considered indigenous to Norway. Of these, two are listed on the 2015 "red list" for endangered species by the Norwegian Biodiversity Information Centre (NBIC): the great crested newt (listed as "nearly threatened") and the pool frog (listed as "critically endangered" as it only occupies 2–3 small lakes in the south of Norway). With the ability to infect hundreds of amphibian species worldwide (Olson et al., 2013), Bd is regarded as a generalist fungal pathogen, presently known to occur in Sweden (Hallengren, 2013) and Denmark (Scalera et al., 2008) with negative laboratory-reported effects on Swedish common toads (Meurling, 2019), but little is known of the virulence potential of the Norwegian species. As the first step, it was therefore important to disclose whether Bd is present in Norway, and we therefore included eDNA sampling to our yearly newt trapping monitoring program in 31 ponds in the Oslofjord area. The objectives of this study were to (i) assess whether any of the monitored Norwegian ponds in the southeastern part of Norway are positive for Bd, and if so, (ii) explore potential population effects in positive ponds for two amphibian species, the great crested newt (*Triturus cristatus*) and the smooth newt (*Lissotriton vulgaris*) through statistical modeling of five years of capture data from trap nets as both species are inhabiting all the investigated ponds and are potential hosts for Bd (Sztatecsny & Glaser, 2011).

2 | MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 | Study area and field protocols

A total of 31 ponds in the southeastern part of Norway were selected as part of an ongoing population monitoring program

of newts. In each pond, we first collected 1 liter of water from 15 stations into a single large container, making a 15 L mix from which we extracted two 0.5 L samples (Figure 1). The two subsamples were filtered through a 0.45-micron filter (Thermo Scientific Nalgene CN 145-0045) using a vacuum pump (Sartorius Microsart e.jet) connected to a 3-place manifold (Pall filter funnel manifold). For some ponds, the amount of filtered water ended up being less than 0.5 L due to clogged filters that slowed or stopped the filtration completely. The final volume was recorded and corrected for when calculating the final eDNA concentrations of Bd and newts in the sample. For some ponds, we collected two independent 15 L batches of water sampled at the same sites and filtered a total of 4 samples from the pond, two for each batch (Supplementary Table S1). After filtration, the filters were placed in 2-ml Eppendorf tubes filled with 1,440 μ l ATL buffer (Qiagen) and stored at room temperature until being processed in the laboratory. One pond (Ottarsrud) was sampled three times during the study (Supplementary Table S1). We also filtered two 0.5 L samples containing regular tap water using the same equipment in the field as negative control samples. The containers used to sample water were cleaned with bleach and boiling water between sample sites, and the boots were placed in a bleach container between stops (minimum 15 min). As a positive control, we also included a water sample from a pond in Uddling in Sweden, where skin swabs and DNA analyses have confirmed about 30% of *Rana dalamatina* to be infected with Bd (Per Nyström, written personal communication). In Sweden, 0.5 L of water was filtered using a handheld syringe and a 0.22- μ m filter unit (Sterivex-GP). After filtering, ATL buffer was added to the Sterivex unit and it was stored at room temperature until processing in the laboratory.

2.2 | DNA extraction and ddPCR

DNA was isolated with DNeasy DNA Blood & Tissue Kit (Qiagen) following the modified protocol of Spens et al. (2017) and eluted in 100 μ l. Published primers and probes for each species were analyzed on a droplet digital PCR (ddPCR, Bio-Rad QX200 AutoDG) for assessing species-specific eDNA concentrations: Bd (Boyle et al., 2004), great crested newt (Thomsen et al., 2012), and smooth newt (Smart et al., 2015). Each assay was run with standard ddPCR conditions and contained 10 μ l ddPCR Supermix for Probes (No dUTP, Bio-Rad Laboratories, Inc.), 3.6 μ M of species-specific primer, 0.86 μ M of species-specific probe, 5.21 μ l dH₂O, and 1 μ l of template DNA, in a total volume of 22 μ l. PCR amplification was conducted on a Veriti Thermal Cycler (Applied Biosystems, Inc.) with an initial denaturation for 10 min at 95°C, followed by 40 cycles of 30 s at 95°C and 1 min at 60°C, and final incubation at 98°C for 10 min. For all runs, we included a negative control (dH₂O as template) and a positive control (DNA from target organism).

QuantaSoft software v.1.7.4 (Bio-Rad Laboratories) was used to separate positive from negative droplets, according to the manufacturer's instructions. To avoid false positives, the detection limit was

FIGURE 1 (a) Map showing the positions of the 31 sampling sites marked as black (Bd-negative) and orange (Bd-positive) points and their location in Norway. (b) Each pond was first sampled for a total of 15 L of water from 15 sampling sites using a beaker, and two samples of 0.5 L were filtrated from the batch of 15 L. The area of water sampling in the pond corresponded to the area that was monitored for catch data using traps. (c) DNA was extracted from the preserved filter and included in a ddPCR. When target DNA is present, the primers amplify the DNA and the reaction results in three or more positive droplets in the ddPCR-analysis

conservatively set to 3 positive droplets (Dobnik et al., 2015). Two locations had two positive droplets and were not regarded as positive: Lahelldammen (one out of 40 samples) and Kittilsrud (one out of 4 samples). All samples were run once for each targeted organism, except the two samples from Østre Støkken (Ø. Støkken) which were run three times for Bd, as these were the first positive samples and were hence used as an additional positive control for the subsequent ddPCR runs (Supplementary Table S1).

2.3 | Capture data from trap nets and statistical modeling

From 2013 to 2017, great crested and smooth newts were systematically monitored by trap nets originally designed for minnows at the same locations as for the eDNA samples. Species and sex were recorded for the trapped animals, before being released back into the pond. For each location, a set of 10 traps were actively catching newts for about 24 hr in the reproductive peak season for the newts. Although the catch data are believed to correlate with the population size, population density, and habitual quality present in the ponds, there are also several other factors that will influence the numbers of individuals in the traps. For ectotherms, such as amphibians, environmental temperature is, for example, directly linked to individual activity and reproduction (see, e.g., Dervo et al., 2016).

Furthermore, pond properties such as size might influence the capture efficiency of the trap in the specific ponds, and we also wanted to control for variation in capture effort (i.e., hours actively capturing). To control for the variation in the catch data as a result of the aforementioned factors, we constructed generalized linear mixed models (glmm) producing capture predictions more likely to portray actual population trends in the ponds. Specifically, we explored individuals captured at catch event i at a specific pond j through multiple candidate models (see Box 1) using this formulation:

$$\text{Captured individuals}_{ij} \sim \text{Poisson}(\mu_{ij})$$

$$\log(\mu_{ij}) = \eta_{ij}$$

$$\eta_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{1ij} + \dots + \beta_n x_{nij} + b_j$$

$$b_j \sim N(0, \sigma_{\text{Pond}}^2)$$

β s represents coefficients under estimation, x s represents potential variables such as water temperature during capture event (also included as a polynomial function in some candidate models), effort (in hours, log-transformed), area (in m^2 , log-transformed), and a potential effect of Bd and year (included as a factor). b_j is the pond specific random intercept. All candidate models (Box 1) were constructed in R (R Core Team, 2020) using the lme4 package (Bates et al., 2014). The coefficient estimates used for predicting population trends were found by performing a model averaging

Box 1 The fixed effect structure of candidate models included in the model averaging procedure to produce parameter estimates to predict population trends for Northern crested newts and smooth newts. All models had pond ID as a random intercept.

Model/ Fixed effect structure

Temperature effect

~ Year + Effort

~ Year + Effort + Temp

~ Year + Effort + Temp-q (quadratic polynomial)

~ Year + Effort + Temp-c (cubic polynomial)

Effects of area and bd

~ Year + Effort + Temp-c + Area

~ Year + Effort + Temp-c + Bd

~ Year + Effort + Temp-c + Area + Bd

procedure over all candidate models using the MuMIn package (Bartoń, 2019).

The difference in eDNA concentrations for the two newt species across the three time points in Ottarsrud was tested with general linear models: trait ~ date, in R (R Core Team, 2020). The results are given as coefficients of the predictor (mean of the difference between the dates), where the *p*-value is calculated based on a likelihood ratio test where the means are forced to be equal against a model that allows them to vary. We also report the differences between the sample dates in Østre Støkken as paired *t* tests.

3 | RESULTS

3.1 | eDNA

Bd was documented in a total of five ponds situated on the eastern side of the Oslo fjord (Figure 1). The eDNA results for the infected ponds are presented as boxplots in Figure 2 and summarized in Supplementary Table S1 as DNA copies L⁻¹. When comparing eDNA levels for Bd across time in Ottarsrud, there was a significant increase in concentration between sampling 1 and sampling 3 ($F_{2,9} = -2566$, $p = .001$, Figure 2a). In contrast, eDNA concentrations for the two newt species decreased over the same period (Figure 2b; great crested newt: $F_{2,9} = 7.6$, $p = .001$, and smooth newt: $F_{2,9} = 5.02$, $p = .03$ (Figure 2b). All pairwise comparisons are given as *t* tests in Table 1.

3.2 | Capture data from trap nets

As we only detected Bd-positive ponds on the eastern side of the Oslo fjord, we only included monitoring data from the 15 sampled

ponds in that geographical area as to reduce the overall natural variation in population estimates. The models used for predicting catches of great crested and smooth newts under standardized temperatures and sampling effort showed no obvious negative population trends in infected ponds ($n = 5$) compared with noninfected ponds ($n = 10$, Figure 3). On the contrary, the models predicted on average higher catches of newts in Bd-infected lakes, but this is likely reflecting the somewhat higher population averages in ponds infected with Bd (smooth newt: 71.65 and 52.62, and great crested newt 22.5 and 10.12, for infected and healthy ponds, respectively; unpublished catch data).

4 | DISCUSSION

A global, genome-wide approach has traced the origin of Bd to East Asia, dating the emergence of the fungi to the early 20th century (O'Hanlon et al., 2018), which corresponds well with the global expansion of commercial trade in amphibians and the occurrence of known global amphibian declines (Scheele et al., 2019). The positive detection of Bd in this study represents the first documentation of these pathogenic fungi in Norway. We do not know when or how Bd invaded the Norwegian ponds, but as Bd is a relatively new species to Sweden (Garner et al., 2005; it was first identified from swab samples in 2009, Hallengren, 2013), a country that has less restrictions on pet trade compared with Norway, the pathogenic fungi are likely in the early phases of establishment also in Norwegian ponds. The Bd-positive ponds are all located within one region of our study area, although they are dispersed in the landscape in-between Bd-negative ponds. We cannot exclude the presence of false negatives in our data (Erickson et al., 2019) as eDNA is known to show "patchy distributions" within environments, but a similar distribution pattern has also been found in other countries, such as Sweden (Kärverno et al., 2018) and the UK (Smith, 2014), that both have hosted Bd for a longer time. Also, in Sweden, the number of ponds with Bd is increasing in line with increasing monitoring time, suggesting that a larger Norwegian sample size and/or sampling at more optimal sampling times would result in a higher number of positive ponds in the Bd-positive area (Kärverno et al., 2018). It is likely that Bd will spread from the known and at present unknown positive locations, but the observed patchy distribution pattern from other countries, having a longer monitoring effort, also suggests that there are factors limiting spread between water bodies or that Bd can become extinct due to natural causes (Kärverno et al., 2020).

The quantitative ddPCR results indicate a seasonal increase in Bd, with eDNA concentrations from the three sampling dates in Ottarsrud being significantly different and increasing with time (Figure 2a). Climate and temperature are linked with Bd virulence, where temperatures in the ranges of 17 and 25°C have been found to give optimal growth for Bd (Piotrowski et al., 2004), and early onset of spring has been found to correlate with high Bd prevalence (Clare et al., 2016). The mean temperature in the Bd-infected ponds in this study was approximately 16°C ($SD = 3^\circ\text{C}$). This is thus close to

FIGURE 2 Boxplot showing eDNA concentrations in pond water for Bd-positive sites. (a) Bd (per L) and (b) great crested and smooth newt (per mL). Ottarsrud was sampled at three different times, where 1, 2, and 3 on the x-axis refer to 21 May, 1 June, and 16 June, respectively. The raw data for each locality have been added as squares to illustrate the specific variation of the samples

TABLE 1 Mean eDNA concentration, standard error (SE), *t* test, degrees of freedom (DF), and *p*-values for the different pairwise comparisons on data from the three sample periods in Østre Stokken

	Comparison	Difference in mean	DF	T-Value	<i>p</i> -Value
Bd	Time 1 and 2	-470.1	3	-0.93	.424
	Time 1 and 3	-2566.4	3	-2.82	.066
	Time 2 and 3	-2095.408	3	-1.95	.14
Great-crested newt	Time 1 and 2	57,020.11	3	1.47	.23
	Time 1 and 3	102,415.4	3	3.27	.046
	Time 2 and 3	45,395.31	3	5.84	.01
Smooth newt	Time 1 and 2	-1324.763	3	-0.191	.859
	Time 1 and 3	19,418.74	3	5.8729	.00984
	Time 2 and 3	20,743.51	3	2.9742	.058

FIGURE 3 Graph illustrating model results of population density based on traditional monitoring data for a) great crested and b) smooth newts in Bd-infected (the lighter gray, upper line) and Bd-free ponds (the darker gray, lower line) with 90% confidence intervals (CI). The catch has been adjusted by temperature, pond area, and the total fishing time for each trap, as these are variables that have been found to significantly alter the number of trapped individuals

the optimal growth temperatures for Bd. The amphibians are more active at temperatures close to their optimums, likely spreading the Bd DNA more efficiently in the water column (Bielby et al., 2015). Also, the persistence of short eDNA fragments can be long lived, up to a month in ponds protected from direct sunlight (Dejean et al., 2011), so a stronger seasonal signal could indicate that eDNA accumulates over time. In contrast, we found decreasing levels of eDNA for both newt species in Ottarsrud (Figure 2b). This pattern weakens the hypothesis of seasonal accumulation of Bd eDNA and also contradicts expectations from other eDNA studies on seasonal changes in concentration for similar species (Buxton et al., 2018). As we only had repeated sampling in one single pond, we cannot conclude whether this is a general pattern for Bd or the newts in this area, but one explanation for the decreasing concentration of newt eDNA could be that Bd is introducing behavioral changes in the adult newts, driving them to escape the aquatic environment and spend an increased amount of time on land due to stress or other undetected effects of the infection (Daverson et al., 2018; Rollins-Smith, 2017).

The detection of the fungus itself (as in this paper) is not proof of disease or of a negative impact on the associated population. Confirmation of a disease diagnosis requires more data, including detecting Bd DNA in the skin of the amphibian combined with observation of clinical disease, death of animals with pathological lesions consistent with disease, and/or indirect evidence (e.g., population decline) (OEI, 2018). All trapped animals seemed healthy, and the population modeling did not reveal any difference in population trends between Bd-positive or Bd-negative ponds, for either great

crested or smooth newts. Factors that determine whether the infectious agents (Bd) will cause disease development within an animal includes strain virulence, host immunity, or susceptibility, and environmental factors (climate, abiotic, and biotic factors) that might suppress or promote virulence in the fungi and/or immunity in the hosts (van Severter & Hochberg, 2017). Thus, different species of amphibians may resist or tolerate the infection, or the environment or other factors may prevent sub-clinical infection resulting in disease. Dramatic amphibian declines resulting from chytridiomycosis have occurred mainly in the tropics of Australia, Mesoamerica, and South America, while other parts of the world, including the warmest (Asia and Africa) and the coolest (Europe and north America), have, despite widespread occurrence of Bd, very low numbers of declines to date that can be attributed to chytridiomycosis (Greener et al., 2020; Scheele et al., 2019). We therefore find it likely that Bd at present has little effect on the Norwegian newt species, resulting either from a short infection history, and/or that the newts are infection-tolerant.

For smooth newt, the prevalence of Bd was very low in the UK, with only 2.9% (53 positive of 1821 screened animals) and 1.7% (14 positive of 814 screened animals) Bd-positive animals in 2008 and 2011, respectively (Smith, 2014). Furthermore, in an experimental setup with high exposures of Bd zoospores, relatively few of the exposed smooth newts were infected, and there were no mortalities for the few individuals that were infected (Smith, 2014). In the same study, Smith (2014) found an even lower prevalence of Bd-infected great crested newts, as only one of the 892 individuals tested positive for Bd across the two study years. The low susceptibility for Bd

in adult crested newts was also confirmed by Greener et al. (2020), where they also screened common toads (*Bufo bufo*) and found that not a single exposed individual was positive for Bd. This is, however, contrary to findings for Swedish common toads that suffered a mortality rate of 60% when infected with Bd after metamorphosis, but had no mortality when exposed as larvae (Meurling, 2019). Also, as a future precaution, there is indirect evidence from modeling studies that predicts the resistance and tolerance of Bd to be nonlinear, meaning that a small increase in pathogenic load could lead to a high mortality rate (Wilber et al., 2017). Also, populations in colder regions, such as the ponds in the present study, might be more susceptible to infection with climate change and warmer temperatures (Rollins-Smith, 2017). The thermal mismatch hypothesis predicts that climate warming will threaten cool-adapted hosts during warmer periods (Cohen et al., 2017), as parasites typically have broader thermal limits than hosts and therefore are better at coping with warming (Rohr et al., 2018). Results from a study on cool-adapted frogs in Brazil indicate that the interaction of warmer temperature and Bd-infection may lead to population declines in the endemic *Ischnocnema parva* (Neely et al., 2020). Recent findings also indicate that Bd-infected amphibians have reduced weight (Cheatsazan et al., 2013; Meurling, 2019), lower diversity of skin microbiota (Bletz et al., 2017), and directional selection on MHC molecules resisting Bd, likely making infected populations vulnerable to other novel pathogens due to lower genetic variance (Kosch et al., 2016).

This paper presents the first finding of the pathogenic fungus Bd in Norway, employing eDNA as a method for species detection. We found that levels of Bd eDNA increased throughout the sampling season, and there are several factors that could have contributed to this result and more sampling is needed to verify the pattern. The results from population modeling of two species of newts do not indicate any population declines in the Bd-positive ponds relative to Bd-negative ponds. However, we also suspect recent invasion of this pathogen to Norway, and the newts might experience little impact due to recent infection and low prevalence, which potentially also could result in false negatives in the present dataset. Future studies should therefore include a higher number of samples per site and/or filter a higher quantity of water, as this has been found to increase the likelihood of detecting rare species (Barnes et al., 2020; Fossøy et al., 2020). This study further highlights the importance of performing regular monitoring and combines traditional methods yielding population estimates with techniques such as eDNA, to detect and potentially react to harmful invasive species early in their invasion phase (Bosch et al., 2015). Invasive species pose a global challenge and represent an increasing threat to native biodiversity, with the potential to eradicate local or endemic species. Although Bd seems to pose a limited risk to the Norwegian newt species at this stage, several factors may contribute to increased disease development and mortality in the future, and measures to reduce the overall stress loads for amphibians should therefore be assessed and enforced as soon as possible to compensate for any negative effects of the new pathogen.

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[Correction added on 24 January 2021, after first online publication: ACKNOWLEDGMENTS section has been updated.]

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no competing interests.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

A.T, B.D, and F.F designed the study. A.T, B.D, and F.F contributed to data collection. A.T and K.M.B analyzed the data. A.T wrote the first draft of the paper. All authors agree to be held accountable for the content of this manuscript.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

This research was approved by the County Governor of Oslo and Akershus. The animals were captured with permission from the Directorate for Nature Management (ref. 2012/3515, 2014/2025, and 2017/1082 ART-VI-ID).

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data are included in Supplementary Table S1.

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information may be found online in the Supporting Information section.

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